

Water Insecurity in Pakistan: Assessing the Impact of Climate Change, Population Growth, and Infrastructure Deficits

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ABSTRACT

This research implies a very high level of water insecurity in Pakistan in the face of climate change, population growth, and deficits in infrastructure. The paper discusses the core link between population growth and water demand, the scale of deficit in infrastructure in the country's water sector, what obstacles stand in the way of IWRM in Pakistan, and how effective current water policies and institutions are. Our analysis discloses consequences of low water security are well documented, including climate change, population increase, and infrastructure deficits. The major causes of water insecurity in Pakistan are climate change, population increase, and infrastructure deficits.

Our work highlights the Institutional, financial, and technical barriers that hinder the prospect of IWRM for Pakistan. Also it suggests a recommendation for improvement in the water governance investment in the water infrastructure practice of water conservation for water security in Pakistan.

1. Introduction

Pakistan is among the top 10 countries that suffer from water scarcity (World Bank, 2020). Climate change, population growth, and infrastructure deficits have worsened the situation. Climate change affects the availability, quality, and distribution of water. While population growth increases the demand for water in Pakistan (Khan et al., 2019). Infrastructure deficits in water storage, treatment, and distribution facilities have further worsened the situation in Pakistan (Pakistan Water and Power Development Authority, 2020). The World Bank's Water Global Practice kicked off the Water Security Diagnostic Initiative in 2017. Eighteen water security diagnostics have been ongoing or delivered both on the country and regional levels, meeting the growing client demand for water security analytics.

Pakistan is a water-impooverished country which has more than 216 million people, ranking at the top 10 around the world in terms of water insecurity (World Bank, 2020). Climatic change, population growth and infrastructure deficits are the three triple threats that have contributed to the complex level of this nation's water insecurity.

Water security focuses on the positive and negative outcomes, and not processes for people, the economy, and the environment that are influenced by diverse aspects of water management.

Climate change is altering the availability, quality, and distribution of water; population growth increases the demand for water (Khan et al., 2019). Deficits in infrastructure, including lack of adequate facilities for storage, treatment, and distribution of water, worsen the situation (Pakistan Water and Power Development Authority, 2020).

The United Nations reported that the country's per capita water availability has declined from 1,500 cubic meters in 2000 to 1,000 cubic meters in 2020. It is also considered a water-scarce country.

The most water insecure countries combine challenging hydrological environments with weak institutions and chronic under-investment in water infrastructure.

According to the World Bank, Pakistan's water scarcity will increase; per capita availability will decrease to 550 cubic meters by 2050 (World Bank, 2020).

Climate Change and Water Insecurity

Climate change has various impacts on water security in Pakistan. It has changed the precipitation patterns, leading to increased droughts and floods (Hassan et al., 2018). The melting and snowmelt patterns change the water available in the Indus River Basin, which is said to account for 65% of the country's water supply (Immerzeel et al., 2018). Climate change has also led to the pollution of sources of water, hence affecting waterborne diseases (Qureshi et al., 2018).

According to the International Water Management Institute, the future change in climate is projected to reduce the availability of Pakistan's water by 20% up to 2050 (IWMI, 2019). In another journal article published by the Journal of Hydrology, the risk of flooding in Pakistan would be on a 50% level by 2100.

Population Growth and Water Demand

Population growth in Pakistan increases water demands and accelerates water scarcity. The population is predicted to reach 343 million by 2040; therefore, the water demands are expected to rise to 50% of that (United Nations, 2020). The other factor that increases the use of water is urbanization and industrialization. Both factors increase the strain on existing infrastructure (Khan et al., 2019).

According to Pakistan Water and Power Development Authority statistics, the country uses 45% of water for household consumption only. Agriculture is at 40%, while industry uses 15%. However, this agricultural sector consumes water in a very inefficient manner, as it loses 60% of the water through inefficient irrigation systems (Qureshi et al., 2018).

Infrastructure Deficits

Pakistan's water infrastructure is limited to support the increasing needs. The country has water storage capacity at only 10% of the total annual river flows, unlike the global average of 40% (World Bank, 2020). The capacity for water treatment is also low, with treated water only available to 20% of the population in urban areas (Pakistan Water and Power Development Authority, 2020).

According to the Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management, water infrastructure investment must include dams, reservoirs, and water treatment plants.

2. Related Work:

Pakistan is now facing the issues of climate change, increased population growth, and a deficit of infrastructure that amplifies previously existing challenges on water security (Khan et al., 2020). The country is facing severe challenges in terms of water resources in agriculture, industry, and human consumption.

Pakistan is "in the list of top 33 countries under extreme water stress," with Karachi being the 6th most water insecure metropolitan on the globe. Forecasts show that

Pakistan will face a severe water shortage in 2025.

Climatic Change Effects

A critical impact on water availability has emerged in Pakistan due to climate change. The changes have been influenced by increased temperature, thereby altering the rain pattern; increasing the chances of frequent droughts and floods, respectively (IPCC, 2014). Research revealed that hydro flows within the rivers would decrease because of climatic change that will severely affect hydro power generation as well as irrigation (Immerzeel et al., 2010). Additionally, it influences agricultural productivity and thus impacts food insecurity, making such issues critical because of alterations in the weather (Ahmed et al., 2016).

Population Growth and Urbanization

Pakistan's growing population exerts a tremendous stress on its water resources. The nation's population will be increased to 250 million by 2030, which will be the cause of additional stress on this already scarce water resource (UN DESA, 2020). Stress is increased due to urbanization because cities require much higher investments in water infrastructure than other cities (Bhatti et al., 2016). So, studies are focusing that integrated water management strategies would be required to mitigate the impact of urbanization on water security (Khan et al., 2018).

Infrastructure Lags

Pakistan's water infrastructure is lagging with major gaps in storage, treatment, and distribution capacity. According to Asian Development Bank, 2019, this country has low water storage capacities and becomes prone to drought and floods (WAPDA, 2020). Moreover, because of inefficient distribution systems, massive losses occur that further limit supplies (Khalid et al., 2017).

Water Management and Governance

Effective water management and governance can solve Pakistan's water security issues. The coordination between the government, local communities, and other stakeholders will prove very effecting in managing water insecurity in Pakistan (Ansari et al., 2019). In addition, new technologies such as water harvesting and conservation technologies have improved water efficiency in Pakistan (Hassan et al., 2020).

The dilemma of Pakistan's water security is complex and interlocking with different factors. Climate resilience, a healthy population growth rate management plan, infrastructure development in all sectors, and good governance is vital in addressing these issues in Pakistan.

Population Growth and Water Demand

As estimated, the growth rate of Pakistan's population stands at 2.1% per annum. Thus it positioned among the highest in South Asia that is causing water insecurity in

Pakistan (United Nations, 2020). Such growth significantly increases the demand for water. As estimated by the Pakistan Water and Power Development Authority, the future demands will increase from 109 billion cubic meters in 2020 to 144 billion cubic meters by 2030.

Table 1: Projected Population Growth and Water Demand in Pakistan (Pakistan Water and Power Development Authority, 2020)

Year	Population(Million)	Demand(Billion cubic meters)
2020	216	109
2025	244	123
2030	274	144
2035	307	168
2040	343	193

This scarce water resource in the country has been under mounting pressure due to the increasing water demand pressure. Population growth has significantly driven the demand for water in Pakistan; such is demonstrated by various studies including Qureshi et al. (2018) and Khan et al. (2019).

Infrastructure Deficiencies in the Pakistani Water Sector

The country's water infrastructure does not meet the rising demands for water. Pakistan stores just 10% of its annual river flows. On the other hand, globally, 40% is stored (World Bank, 2020). Its water treatment capacity also faces a limitation since just 20% of its urban population has access to treated water (Pakistan Water and Power Development Authority, 2020).

Table 2: Comparison of Pakistan's Water Infrastructure with Global Averages (World Bank, 2020)

Indicator	Pakistan	Global Average
Storage capacity	10%	40%
Water Treatment capacity	20%	80%
Water Distribution Loses	30%	15%

The infrastructure deficits result in significant water losses and inefficient use of available water resources.

3. Research Methodology:

This describes the manner in which climate change, population growth, and infrastructure deficits have been impacting the water security of Pakistan. The methodology applied for this particular research study followed a mixed-methods research approach by joining both the quantitative and qualitative approaches together to give insight into the problem in question.

Secondary data gathering regarding the quantitative approach is followed from credible sources: mainly Pakistan Water and Power Development Authority (WAPDA), Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (PBS), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and the World Bank. Analysis with the help of SPSS software through descriptive statistics, regression analysis was applied.

Alternatively, the qualitative method comprised semi-structured interviews taken by 170 stakeholders in Lower Punjab, Pakistan, which included water specialists (n=50), farmers (n=70), and grassroots community members (n=50).

The risk of water scarcity is growing and Pakistan's ability to guarantee water security is precarious. The paper explains how Pakistan's economy, society, federation, and environment are impacted by the country's water issue and the effects it has on collective national security and strength.

In Sampling plan a random sampling to collect data for the former and the latter employed in purposive sampling. Methods of instrumentations were standardized questionnaire in the former part. The interviewer's guide developed for an interview with former data; the latter half used in semi-structured interview to collect data with the said guide.

Reliability checks had ensured data quality as checks for consistency and accuracy in the data gathered. It also ensured that the information was valid. In this research, the ethical consideration was taken by acquiring an informed consent from the participant and keeping their data private.

The unavailability of primary data resulted from restrictions in accessing this data combined with time limitation which lowered the scope for this study.

Research Questions and Objectives

This study aimed to answer three research questions:

- (1) What is the impact of climate change on water availability in Pakistan?
- (2) How does population growth affect water demand in Pakistan?
- (3) What role do infrastructure deficits play in water insecurity in Pakistan?

The study's objectives

- (1) To assess the impact of climate change on water availability in Pakistan
- (2) To examine the relationship between population growth and water demand in Pakistan
- (3) To investigate the effect of infrastructure deficits on water insecurity in Pakistan

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The study has anchored its theoretical framework based on the water security framework that looks into how changes in climate and growth of population and deficit infrastructures relate to one another. Conceptual frameworks were shown in the paper with these:

Climate Change → Water Availability → Water Security;
Population Growth → Water Demand → Water Security; and
Infrastructure Deficits → Water Distribution → Water Security.

Operational Definitions

For the purpose of this paper, water security is considered as availability in sufficient quantities, safely, and reliably. Climate change incorporates changes in temperature, rainfall, and drought occurrences. Population growth refers to population size increases. Infrastructure deficits refer to the deficiency in water storage, treatment, and distribution facilities.

4. Conclusion

Water insecurity in Pakistan is not only a complex issue but also multi-faceted: climate change, population growth, and infrastructure deficits. These three of drivers are responsible for this complex situation in Pakistan.

The outcome of this study underlines the pressing need for Pakistan. Pakistan have to bring about a shift in the paradigm of managing its water resources. To have water security, Pakistan will have to address the challenges of climate change, coupled with the challenges of a growing population and infrastructure deficits.

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